

Survey on Barriers and Obstacles to OA Publishing for Researchers with Weak Institutional Ties

Section 1. Demographic questions

1. **What gender do you identify with?**
 - Female
 - Male
 - Binary
 - Other
 - I prefer not to share
2. **What age range do you fit into?**
 - 18 to 24
 - 25 to 34
 - 35 to 44
 - 45 to 54
 - 55 to 64
 - 65 or over
 - I prefer not to share
3. **Which geographical location do you work and publish from mainly?**
4. **What is your current employment status?**
 - Unemployed
 - Employed in Academia
 - Employed in Academia but conduct and publish independent research
 - Employed by a private company
 - Employed by non-governmental organization (NGO)
 - Employed by governmental institution
 - Employed by a hospital or clinic
 - Self-employed (Consultancy etc.)
 - Pensioner
 - Phd Student
 - University/college student
 - I prefer not to share
 - Other
 - 4.1 ***If you are employed in academia, what is your position?***
 - Technical / administrative staff
 - Research assistant
 - Postdoc
 - Professor (Assistant, Associate, Full)
 - I prefer not to share
 - Other
5. **What is your current highest academic degree?**
 - No degree
 - Bachelor degree (or equivalent)
 - Master degree (or equivalent)

- Doctor / PhD
- Medical Doctor
- I prefer not to share
- Other

6. What type of researcher do you identify with most?

- Pensioner researcher / Retired researcher
- Citizen Scientist
- Researcher for a small and/or private university
- Refugee scientist/ temporarily displaced researcher
- Independent researcher
- Researcher working for NOG
- Researcher working for Industry enterprises
- Medical doctor/nurse/clinician
- I prefer not to share
- Other

6.1. (If Pensioner researcher / Retired researcher) Do you still make use of your previous employers affiliation while publishing?

- Yes, I do
- No, I do not

6.2 (If Citizen Scientist) Please specify your role as a Citizen science actor?

- I am not financially compensated for my work
- I am financially compensated for my work

Section 2. Open Access publishing

1. Is publishing open access important to you?

- It is extremely important to me
- It is very important to me
- It is somewhat important to me
- It is not very important to me
- It is not important to me at all
- It does not make any difference to me

2. What type of open access publishing is most relevant to you?

- OA journal publishing
- OA monograph publishing
- Depositing in open institutional repositories
- OA conference proceedings
- Preprint servers
- Social media
- Other

3. Have you ever published open access?

- Yes, I have

- No, I have not
 - I do not know, I was not a corresponding author
4. **How informed are you on the subject of open access publishing?**
- Very uninformed
 - Uninformed
 - Somewhat uninformed
 - Somewhat informed
 - Informed
 - Very informed
5. **Practical Barriers. What is preventing you from publishing open access (OA)? (Choose all that apply)**
- High article processing charge
 - I have no funding to cover article processing fees
 - OA publishing brings extensive administrative burden
 - There are not enough reputable OA journals within my research domain
 - I lack access to programs required by publishers to make a submission (e.g. Microsoft Office etc.)
 - Slow or unavailable internet connection, making it difficult to engage with OA publishing
 - Unreliable or lack of access to electricity
 - Lack of subscription access to English-language journals so I cannot prepare up-to-date research
 - There is no established subject repository in my research domain
 - My institution does not have an institutional repository
 - I cannot afford participation in foreign conferences (visa, accommodation cost, etc.)
 - It takes extra efforts to self-archive/preprint a paper
 - My research was deemed unsuitable for publication because it focused on a niche topic based on location
 - Pre-registered databases on publishing platforms do not list "independent researcher" as an affiliation status
 - My paper was desk-rejected because of my affiliation status
 - None of the above
6. **Sentiment. What is preventing you from publishing open access (OA)? (Choose all that apply)**
- OA journals are of a low quality
 - OA papers are of low prestige
 - OA journals have lower impact factor than paywalled journals
 - OA articles are at a high risk of being plagiarized, scooping or misused
 - Many of OA journals are predatory with low scholarly rigor
 - I believe that OA papers are cited less, but I want to get recognition for my work
 - I believe that OA papers have lower readership than subscription based content
 - I believe that research articles should only be shared with those who can understand it
 - OA journals are poorly preserved
 - It is not prestigious to publish in repositories

- I would prefer not to share research which has not been peer reviewed
 - I do not think it is important or necessary to add my paper to a repository
 - I am afraid that publishing OA may have long-term negative consequences for my career
 - It is not me who decides where to publish, my supervisor/co-author advises against publishing OA
 - I have no trust in diamond open-access as it is a novice option that has not been tested sufficiently
 - Uncertainty about copyright and concerns over breaching publishing rights
 - None of the above
7. **Lack of Competency. What is preventing you from publishing open access (OA)? (Choose all that apply)**
- I do not know how to publish OA
 - I am not sure how to deposit in a repository
 - My English is not good enough to publish OA
 - I received a review report in which credibility of my research was questioned due to my affiliation status
 - None of the above
8. **Policy and Governance. What is preventing you from publishing open access (OA)? (Choose all that apply)**
- I have no incentives to publish OA
 - There are no rewards for publishing OA
 - I face legal barriers for OA publishing
 - I want to retain copyright and copyright retention policies from the publisher side are unclear
 - I am not eligible for an APC waiver
 - APC waiver policies are inconsistent and not transparent from the publishers side
 - OA journals are not indexed in preferable databases
 - I do not get any support from my institution
 - I am overwhelmed with my teaching or other duties and have limited time available for research and publishing
 - There is not enough mentoring for Early Stage Researchers on how to publish OA properly
 - My country is under economic sanctions of the USA, European Union so I cannot pay APC
 - I am prohibited from using external storage devices (USB Sticks/Flash drives)
 - None of the above

Section 3. In-depth Questions

1. **How compatible do you find industry oriented research with open access publishing?**
- Very incompatible
 - Incompatible
 - Somewhat incompatible
 - Somewhat compatible
 - Compatible

- Very compatible
2. **Have you collaborated, or have you considered collaborating, with researchers who have APC funds to publish Gold open access?**
 - Yes, and I have done it once
 - Yes, I have done it several times
 - Yes, this is my main strategy of getting my research published
 - No, I have not, but I considering of doing so
 - No, I have never done it and will not do it
 3. **Are you comfortable sharing your private address with the publisher?**
 - Yes, I do
 - No, I do not
 - I have an affiliation and share that address
 4. **Have you ever taken part in an open access publishing training or workshop?**
 - Yes, I have
 - No, I have not
 - Other
 5. **If yes, was this training or workshop organized or offered to you through your current affiliation?**
 - Yes, it was offered through my affiliation
 - No, it was not offered through my affiliation but it does offer OA publishing training and workshops
 - No, my affiliation does not offer OA publishing trainings or workshops
 - No, I do not have an affiliation

